

CALCULATION MODEL OF THE EFFICIENCY OF THE MEANS OF PROTECTION AGAINST THE ELECTROMAGNETIC FIELD (BY THE EXAMPLE OF A TRAIN DISPATCH WORKSTATION)

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Annotation: The increase in the number and power of various artificial sources (radio communication, VDT and personal computer, uninterruptible power supply, etc.) lead to a significant increase in the level of electromagnetic radiation in the workplace, which create an additional artificial electromagnetic field that adversely affects human health. One of the most reliable ways to protect against electromagnetic fields is to shield these equipments. The article developed a calculation model for calculating the effectiveness of the screen from the effects of electromagnetic fields at the workplace of a train dispatcher.

Key words: electromagnetic fields, uninterruptible power supply, shielding, electrical, dielectric and magnetic conductivity, protective cover and screen, calculation scheme and model.

Introduction and problem statement. Emissions of harmful and dangerous factors at the workplace of a train dispatcher are formed in connection with the indicators of technical means. The electromagnetic field at the workplace of a train dispatcher is mainly created by VDT and personal computers, which dispatchers regularly use in their work, as well as electromagnetic waves emitted by an uninterruptible power supply [1,2].

The measurements carried out during the certification of workplaces for working conditions showed that the voltage of the electromagnetic field in the workplace of a train dispatcher is mainly created by an uninterruptible power supply that provides power to the VDT and personal computers at the workplace. The uninterruptible power supply is located inside the desktop cabinet, and the chair on which the dispatcher sits is placed next to it, due to the need to constantly monitor data from monitors [3].

One of the most reliable ways to protect against electromagnetic fields is to shield these equipments. When creating structures that protect against electromagnetic field strength, various materials (metal or dielectric) are used, which have the property of absorbing or repelling an electromagnetic field in a certain frequency range [4,5,6,7].

The absorption efficiency of an electromagnetic field is determined by the electrical, dielectric and magnetic properties of the material used for shielding. Due to these properties of the material, electromagnetic energy is absorbed due to dielectric, magnetic and conduction losses. Shielding allows you to reduce the level of electromagnetic field strength to a safe level [8].

Theory and research methods. Shielding separates magnetic, electric and electromagnetic fields. In most cases, the same dielectric medium is located on both sides of the screen, and in this case, the screen efficiency is written as follows [9]:

$$e = 20lg|chkh| + 20lg \left| 1 + 0,5 \left(\frac{z_2}{z_1} + \frac{z_1}{z_2} \right) thkh \right|, \quad (1)$$

where h – screen thickness, mm; k – spread coefficient, mm^{-1} ;

z_1 – medium resistance to electromagnetic field, Ohm;

z_2 – resistance of the screen material to the electromagnetic field, Ohm.

However, the impedance z_1 in the induction zone depends not only on the type of the main component of the electromagnetic field, but also on the shape of the screen structure.

Given the shape of the screen, the impedance z_1 is written as follows [10]:

When shielding the electric field:

$$|z_1| = \frac{1}{\omega \varepsilon_1 r_* m} \quad (2)$$

When shielding the magnetic field:

$$|z_1| = \omega \mu_1 r_* m, \quad (3)$$

where $m=2$ at $r_* = \frac{L}{2}$ for flat screen, $m=1$ at $r_* = \rho$ for cylindrical screen,

$m = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$ at $r_* = r$ for a spherical screen.

When shielding a magnetic field, it is necessary to take into account the characteristics of the material from which the shield is made. Usually for

magnetic materials (steel, permalloy, ferrite) $\frac{z_2}{z_1} > \frac{z_1}{z_2}$, and for non-magnetic

materials (copper, aluminum, lead) $\frac{z_2}{z_1} < \frac{z_1}{z_2}$. Provided that at relatively low

frequencies of the electromagnetic field ($f < 10^4 Hz$) $kh \ll 1$, $chkh \approx 1$, $thkh \approx kh$ for protective devices made of magnetic metals, the shielding efficiency is calculated by the formula [11,12,13]:

$$e = 20lg \left[1 + \frac{1}{2m} \cdot \frac{\mu_2}{\mu_1} \cdot \frac{h}{r_*} \right] \quad (3)$$

It does not depend on the frequency of the field.

For protective devices made of non-magnetic metals, the shielding efficiency is calculated by the formula [14,15,16]:

$$e = 10 \lg \left[1 + \frac{m}{2} \cdot \omega \mu_1 \sigma_1 r_* h \right] \quad (4)$$

This efficiency depends on frequency and at frequency $\omega \rightarrow 0$ also tends to zero.

In the region of relatively high frequencies $10^4 < f, \Gamma_{\text{ц}} < 10^9$ shielding efficiency is conveniently determined by the formula [9]:

$$e = 8,686 \sqrt{\frac{\omega \mu_2 \sigma_2}{2}} h + 20 \lg \left[\frac{1}{4} \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_2}{\omega \mu_2} |z_1|} \right] \quad (5)$$

In the microwave region, covering decimeter, centimeter and millimeter waves ($f \geq 10^9 \dots 10^{10}$ Hz), wavelength λ commensurate with the screen diameter d and $\lambda \geq d$, and shielding efficiency is oscillatory.

If there are holes or slits in the screen, resulting from the imperfection of its design and manufacturing technology, the shielding efficiency is reduced. In this case, it can be determined by the formula [17,18]:

$$e = 10 \lg \left| \frac{\sqrt{2z_1}}{z_2} \right| + A + 8,686B \quad (6)$$

where is the impedance z_1 is determined by formulas (2):

$$|z_1| = \left| \sqrt{\frac{\omega \mu_2}{\sigma_2}} \right| \quad (7)$$

The term A and the multiplier B take into account the leakage of the screen:

$$A = 20 \lg \left[\left(\frac{2\pi}{k_1 r_*} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \cdot (1 - 0,5k_1 l)^6 \right] \quad (8)$$

$$B = \frac{2\pi h}{l}, \quad (9)$$

where $r_* \approx 0,62v^{\frac{1}{3}}$ equivalent screen radius of any geometric shape (v - screen internal volume, mm³), mm;
 l - the largest size of the hole (slot) in the screen, mm;

$$k_1 = \omega \sqrt{\mu_0 \varepsilon_0} \quad (10)$$

Results of the study and their discussion. When developing a scheme for calculating the effectiveness of a protective screen (Figure 1), it was based on a convenient technical layout of the dispatcher's workplace and theoretical formulas for calculating the effectiveness of the above means of protection against electromagnetic fields.

Figure 1. Scheme for calculating protective screens to reduce the level of intensity of the electromagnetic field of the source of the electromagnetic field. The working surface of the workplace of the train dispatcher consists of two parts, one of which is equipped with a desktop with train schedules. Monitors are installed on the rest of the desktop to keep track of information. An uninterruptible power supply is located inside the desktop cabinet, consisting of a mini-transformer and a current rectifier, which regularly supplies power to the VDT and personal computers. Despite the low power of the uninterruptible power supply, it is very close to the place where the dispatcher is located. Therefore, it should be noted that the voltage of the electromagnetic field propagating from it is much higher than the permissible voltage level of the electromagnetic field. It is known that the shielding of an uninterruptible power supply as a means of protection against the effects of electromagnetic field strength is a simple and inexpensive simple device [10].

Reducing the strength of the electromagnetic field of an uninterruptible power supply can be achieved by covering its body with a protective casing and shielding the inner surfaces of the walls of the desktop cabinet [19,20,21].

The effectiveness of the shield and casing in shielding was evaluated according to formula (4) above.

The developed calculation model is two-dimensional, and the shape of the casing and the screen are different from each other. The casing has a semi-cylindrical shape. The inner surfaces of the walls of the desktop pedestal are flat. When mathematically expressing the effectiveness of the calculation model, it is necessary to take into account the design parameters, the shape of the protective equipment (cylindrical casing and flat screen). Given the logarithmic expression of efficiency, it is recommended to use the following mathematical expression based on formula (4) to evaluate the overall effectiveness of the protective cover and screen:

$$e_{ym} = 10lg \left[1 + \frac{m_c}{2} \omega \mu_1 \sigma_1 r_* h \right] + 10lg \left[1 + \frac{m_{\pi}}{2} \omega \mu_1 \sigma_1 r_* h \right], \quad (11)$$

where m_c - sphere shape factor; $\omega = 2\pi f$ - circular frequency, s^{-1} ; μ - absolute magnetic permeability, Gn/m ; σ - medium conductivity, Sm/m ; r_* - equivalent screen radius of any geometric shape, mm ; h - screen thickness, mm ; m_{π} - flat shape factor.

Thus, the use of screens (cylindrical casing and flat screen) to reduce the level of electromagnetic field strength, i.e. covering the source provides an increase in the effectiveness of the protection means.

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